

VISUAL IDENTITY OF UKRAINIAN TERRITORIAL COMMUNITIES

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Abstract. The relevance of studying the features of visual identification of united territorial communities in Ukraine in the context of graphic design during the decentralization reform and processes of digitization and designification of society gains particular importance. United territorial communities (hereinafter UTCs, territorial communities, communities) become a key element of Ukrainian statehood and an important factor in the sustainable development of territories. These processes urge researchers to pay special attention to the formation of territorial brands, which contribute to strengthening the local identity of communities, increasing the investment attractiveness of territories, shaping a modern visual space, and the visual culture of territories.

Keywords: visual identification, territorial communities, digitization, designification.

A request for the currently sought-after service of high-quality development of the visual identification of United Territorial Communities (UTCs) is coming from various interested parties, including government bodies, local self-government authorities, community residents, investors, and local businesses. A favorable territorial community brand, its presence in the information space, and effective design of community identity carriers will attract potential investors. This, in turn, will help develop the economic potential of the community, strengthen its competitive positions, and create additional advantages in the economic space. It is a crucial element that ensures social stability by increasing the self-esteem of residents and promoting further reinforcement of local identity.

The formation of local visual community identity requires the integration of individuals and territorial communities with their own local identity, social, historical, cultural, and economic specificity into new social relationships emerging in the community. The design of the visual-graphic code of UTC aims at enhancing local identity, i.e., the self-identification of individuals with the local community based on cultural-psychological unity of the population and best practices in visual communications. As of 2021, Ukraine had 1469 communities formed through the amalgamation of villages, towns, and cities. The trend of forming their own visual

identity prompts UTCs to search for effective solutions in the fields of management, marketing, and graphic design.

The author's developed guidelines for the visual style of Plodorodnenska (Zaporizhia region), Shahivska (Donetsk region), Pyriatynska (Poltava region), and elements of the visual identification of Shyroktivska (Zaporizhia region) and Lymanska (Donetsk region) communities allow identifying certain patterns in the processes of creating territorial brands.

1. Гайдлайн візуального стилю Плodorодненської громади (Запорізька область): елементи айдентики, Стратегія розвитку громади, Інвестиційний паспорт
 2. Брендбук Пирятинської громади (Полтавська область): елементи айдентики, сувенірна брендвана продукція, фірмові патерни, система візуальної навігації
 3. Логобук Шахівської громади (Донецька область): елементи айдентики, оформлення соціальних мереж, Програма і Стратегія розвитку громади

Fig. 1. Guidelines for the visual style of Ukrainian communities (by A. Vynogradova)

Graphic design becomes an effective tool for shaping territorial identity and local brands. Territorial identity emerges at the turn of the 20th-21st centuries at the intersection of various disciplines: marketing, international economics, management, tourism, and graphic design. Active attempts to develop territorial identity in the CIS countries began in the 2010s. Notable foreign researchers include Simon Anholt (USA), Keith Dinnie (UK), Philip Kotler (USA), Mihalis Kavaratzis (UK), Gregory J. Eshvort (UK), John D. Hunt (USA), Árpád Ferenc Papp-Váry (Hungary), Dipak Raj Pant (Italy), Maja Konečnik Ruzzier (Slovenia). The role of design in the tourism sector is discussed in the textbook by J. Holloway and N. Taylor (2007), which briefly outlines the application of graphic design and provides examples of its impact on increasing demand for tourism services.

In Ukraine, territorial branding is explored by researchers primarily from the perspectives of marketing, management (H. H. Mykhailchenko), international economics (H. H. Polishko), public administration and administration (O. N. Yevtushenko, S. M. Verba), economic-legal issues of regional development (V. A. Ustyomenko, I. V. Zablodska, S. O. Burbelo, D. V. Zablodska, P. O. Saenko), geography and tourism (O. Trotsenko, O. Oliynyk), social communications (V. V. Voronova), touching on certain aspects of graphic design.

In a textbook by a group of Ukrainian authors, developed with the support of the Council of Europe's Program on Decentralization and Territorial Consolidation in Ukraine, theoretical and practical aspects of forming the resource potential of territorial communities are outlined. It defines community territory branding as "the process of forming and managing a brand, including its creation, strengthening, promotion, updating, possible repositioning, and rebranding."

Theoretical and methodological foundations of city branding are reflected in the article by Ukrainian researchers O. Bilovodska and N. Haydabrus. Researcher O. Kusraeva defines the main functions of branding since its recognition as a separate scientific direction in the present and presents the functionality that has developed in branding due to the "emergence of new information and communication technologies." However, the issue of visual identification of territorial branding in the context of graphic design is almost not considered by domestic scientists and requires current research.

The contemporary social-information space is saturated with visual images. Some are desired, but most are unwanted, contributing to what is known as "visual noise." All these visual objects, their supplements, and deficiencies create a visual environment where every detail we see (colors, signs, navigation elements, murals, billboards, information signs) becomes expressive, assimilated, normalized, obvious, localized, and accessible. The visual culture of a territory is a way of creating individual identities and collective belonging, a path to peace, order, stability, and progress. Simultaneously, it is a means of manipulation, imposing thoughts, and standardization. Visual culture is a crucial component of modern life, and every individual must navigate and adapt to the visual world around them.

In contemporary culture, visual-communicative forms dominate communication. The communication between a brand and a consumer is no exception. Branding actively utilizes the opportunities of graphic design to build long-term relationships with consumers. One component involves creating the visual-graphic image of the brand. Community identification occurs by highlighting a series of its parameters as a system with its characteristics of integrity, autonomy, functionality, openness, dialogical nature, and mobility in perceiving external meanings of space. The typology of territorial branding (brand identification) can be constructed considering duality that arises when differentiating identification systems into visual-graphic language and visual-graphic style, corresponding to a similar theory of information differentiation into semantic and aesthetic. Both levels coexist within the same communication object, which initiates a communicative act through:

- Recognizability of the territory (what this place is).
- Semantic content and messages (values, messages, ideology).
- Emotions (positive perception and impressions of the place).

The structure of the typology of territorial brands consists of two levels: sense creation and form creation. The visual-graphic code is defined through the semantic meaning of the image element, what is determined by the concept of "content." The aesthetic or artistic level can be defined in terms of the designer's expressive means, aesthetic and stylistic features, and the character of the brand, what is determined by the concept of "form." Visual-graphic stylistics has a "metastructural" nature, meaning it can be applied to various types of solutions. While, in certain cases, it may include a similar set of images, it encompasses a much broader visual-graphic language, as it involves emotions. In addition to the standard set of values or "objective" messages, it actively works with subjective messages (and channels of influence) – emotions. This channel of communication gains significant communicative importance since the subject of the communication process is a person, whose emotional nature often serves as motivation for real action. The nature of the form can guide emotions in a certain way through aesthetic influence: bright or neutral colors, sharp or smooth forms, etc.

Territorial brand identification is a complex message that is structurally unified for the viewer but typologically differentiated for the specialist. Brand identification is structurally formed by two interrelated components: semantic and visual components, analogous to the problem of content and form in visual arts.

A comprehensive approach in territorial branding involves the formation of the territory brand and its identity as an aspect that includes a broad complex of pre-project studies in search of identity, marketing, and territory analysis, as well as the development of a long-term development plan. It implies extensive interdisciplinary collaboration (marketers, designers, historians, tourism and service experts, public relations and advertising professionals, journalists, bloggers, political technologists, economists, etc.) – the union of brand partners for its development, including representatives of the government, business, and local residents. This

approach is highly necessary for domestic practice, as well as its formulation for scientific activity, as national territorial brands often fail due to a superficial approach to branding, leading to ineffective measures.

The historical approach to forming territorial identity is based on the transformation, modification, or other forms of replication of heraldry (coats of arms) and vexillology (flags, standards) – an alternative territorial identity. In some cases, it is applied in conjunction with a modern approach to forming territorial identity, which we distinguish separately. Examples include the visual attributes of brands like Switzerland, Canada, Denmark, or the logo of Zaporizhzhia (see Fig. 2).

Fig 2. *Historical Approach to Forming the Tourist Brand of the City of Zaporizhzhia, Dmytro Bulanov Creative Bureau, 2017.*

Abstract-graphic approach to forming territorial identity is a method of shaping the visual-graphic identity of a place based on abstract compositions, where recognizable objects or replicas of state symbols, especially historical ones, are scarcely traced. The emphasis is placed on emotional and sensory perception, achieved through the use of form, color, composition, and other graphic elements. Typically, these are abstract graphic compositions with the use of specific graphic or abstract symbols. Examples include the logos and graphic symbols of Prague, New York, Berlin. There are also mixed types of graphic symbols for cities, such as Pula (Croatia), which can be classified as abstract-graphic but includes elements of the historical approach, incorporating a cross found in both state symbolism and alternative identity of the country.

Fig. 3. *Abstract-Graphic Approach to the Formation of Ukrainian Territorial Brands*

National-Ethnic Approach to the formation of territorial identity is a method that shapes the graphic identity of a place using dominant visual attributes of one or several nations inhabiting the territory – the national component. This can include folk ornaments, distinctive graphic forms, color schemes characteristic of the lifestyle of a particular nation, as well as combinations of these elements (see fig. 4).

Fig. 4. *National-Ethnic Approach to the Formation of Ukrainian Territorial Brands. Formation of the Tourist Brand of Lviv Region., Happydesign*

The principle of semantics is exemplified in the meaning of the logo of Genichesk. The graphic language of Genichesk's identity is based on the concise form of a rhombus. This geometric and expressive figure is encountered in several images associated with the features and unique aspects of the resort town, namely in the crystals of Sivash salt, the sturgeon scale, and the structure of the Genichesk railway bridge, which is one of the main historical landmarks and symbols of the city. The five symbols of the seaside resort town of Genichesk correspond to its history and features: the sea, as it is primarily a seaside resort; an anchor, representing the Genichesk seaport; birds that migrate to these warm lands for winter; the Genichesk lighthouse; the flounder, as one of the symbols of the Azov Sea, reminding us that from its inception, the city thrived on fishing. All these symbols, within rhombic figures, form a unified composition resembling a bridge. This refers to one of the city's symbols, the old Railway bridge, which has a characteristic rhombic shape in its structure. The name of the city, where these features are located, is presented in the form of massive (like bridge supports) and at the same time playful, uniquely shaped letters. This visual representation of the city of Genichesk is reflected in the letters, combining history and modernity. The slogan, as a concluding message, answers the questions "where to?" and "what to do?" – it is an invitation to visit the tourist city of Genichesk, which serves as a bridge to relaxation.

Fig. 5. Components of the logo of Genichesk

One of the classical methods of logo design is highlighting the first letter of the brand (the name of the territory) in a graphic symbol. Examples of this approach in visual-graphic code design can be found in the logos of several Ukrainian cities – Kalush, Mykolaiv, Nizhyn, Drohobych, Uzhhorod (see Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Method of Modeling a Logo by Highlighting the First Letter of the Brand in a Graphic Symbol

The visual-graphic code of territorial brand identity is a stable element of territory representation in the brand's visual communication system. Visual-graphic style is characterized by greater variability and dynamism; it can be influenced by fashion trends in graphic design and visual arts, which, in turn, shape a certain type of relationship (production, transmission, and perception of communicative objects) within the mainstream. Within one language template, there are various visual-graphic, compositional, and design solutions. The choice of one visual-graphic solution over another is determined by the brand's strategic goals. An analysis of different solutions in territorial brand identity, which, of course, are not exhausted by the examples considered, shows that stylistically, technologically, and conceptually, territorial brands are identical to all the trends that define the nature of modern corporate branding. Despite the unique features of each territory, the tools and solutions within these tools are universal in their functions and methods. Thus, territorial brand identity, despite its specific characteristics, can be characterized as a holistic and global phenomenon. Due to the mentioned morphological identity of territorial brand identity with commercial and corporate design, a number of stylistic, structural, and functional directions for the development of this area should be highlighted. Stylistic typology can be presented within three main directions: "old school," logos 2.0, and flat design.

Old School Graphics. The term "old school" regarding the design of trademarks and logos developed in the 60s-80s of the 20th century can be used quite conditionally. Moreover, many designers who created signs and logos at that time continue to work today. The style of "old school" signs and logos is expressed in monochrome, two-dimensionality, absence of complex visual effects, etc., determined not only by the existing conceptual paradigms at that time but also by technical limitations, which were truly lifted only with the use of digital means of design

product production and reproduction. Among the bright representatives and classics of the "old school," designers like Paul Rand, Saul Bass, Milton Glaser, the author of the I♥NY logo, can be highlighted. Examples of brand identifiers stylistically close to the "old school" are the logos of Poland created and used by the Polish Tourist Organization (2011) and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Poland (2009).

Fig. 6. Old School Graphics in Territorial Visual Identity

Logos web 2.0. The feature of the so-called "web 2.0" style is that the "screen" internet aesthetics is transferred to traditional graphics and offline communication, demonstrating modern corporate rebranding. The graphics of "old school" signs were usually two-dimensional, flat, monochrome. Modern identity designed in the "web 2.0" style is characterized by volume, multicolor, graphic effects, shadows, smoothing, and gradients. This is caused not only by the repeated increase in the resolution of reproduction and transmission means but also by a change in corporate needs that are increasingly integrated into the digital environment, where traditional graphics developed for paper media ceases to be as functional.

One characteristic example of this style is the brand identity of Melbourne (Landor Australia, 2009). The reason for Melbourne's rebranding was the moral aging of the previous logo and the desire of Melbourne's mayor to make the city an "innovative and strong brand." The old logo was graphically unexpressive, narrative (a series of meaningful figures were listed: the sun, feather, column, component of the second leg of the letter "M"), plastic and inconspicuous. Such a logo was lost in the visual environment or perceived as too official and dry. The new logo abandoned the narrative and "compressed" into a monogram. The first letter in the city's name "M" is stylized as a crystal with complex graphics and the overlay of semi-transparent planes. The brand identity of the city of Zhytomyr is also resolved in a smoothed multicolor, with characteristic color gradients, graphics, etc.

Fig. 7. "Web 2.0" Style in Territorial Visual Identity

The associative series is a meaning-creating element of territorial branding, and

design is responsible for shaping the brand identity. The problem of template language in territorial branding lies in the loss of uniqueness and distinctiveness. In fact, uniqueness is set by the aesthetic characteristics of visual identity systems and their visual-plastic solutions within existing templates. This leads to a recognizable "sameness" of solutions that are subject to typologization and communicative framing. Thus:

- Visual-graphic language and visual-graphic style may have unequal significance for different professional design fields (marketing, design, etc.).
- In the field of visual communications and graphic design, priority is given to the visual-graphic style applied to various units of the visual-graphic language.
- The visual-graphic style obtains independent meaning, independent of the formed language of templates, and uses its own template language, including artistic, stylistic, and constructive solutions.

The visual-graphic style carries representative functions within the framework of a cohesive communicative system of territorial branding. Defining the qualitative differences and unity of all structural elements of the brand as a cohesive communicative message requires establishing the relationship between art and communication. The visual-graphic code becomes a mechanism for forming the communicative language of territorial representation through symbolic means.

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